

Highlights

Direct measurements of Rayleigh wave acoustoelastic constants for shot-peened superalloys

Sergey Gartsev, Bernd Köhler

- Acoustoelastic constants (AEC), demanded for surface-treated alloy characterization using Rayleigh waves, may be obtained through direct measurements and indirect mapping using bulk wave AEC.
- Mapping between bulk and surface wave acoustoelastic constants (AEC) does not match up; therefore, the direct AEC measurements should be used for evaluation of the stress–strain state in the vicinity of the surface.
- Treatment may affect not only the RW AEC absolute value but also the sign.
- If ultrasonic testing NDE methods are used, the AEC must be determined for the given state of material (treatment and plastic deformation).

Direct measurements of Rayleigh wave acoustoelastic constants for shot-peened superalloys

Sergey Gartsev^{a,*}, Bernd Köhler^a

^aFraunhofer IKTS (Institut für Keramische Technologien und Systeme), Maria Reiche Straße 2, 01109 Dresden, Germany

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:
Rayleigh waves
Shot peening
Acoustoelastic constants
In-situ measurements

ABSTRACT

In this article, the experimental investigation of the dependency of surface wave (Rayleigh wave) acoustoelastic constants (AEC) on surface treatment parameters and plastic deformation is discussed. These constants are necessary for the monitoring of surface treatment intensity by means of ultrasonic testing. The indirect (mapping of bulk wave AEC to the surface wave AEC through the Grüneisen constants) method and the direct method are compared. Also the Rayleigh wave AEC have been directly measured for the different states of material (annealed, plastically deformed, or surface treated) for In718 and Ti6246 alloys. We show that surface AEC are very sensitive to any changes in material structure, up to changes in the sign of the effect, and for practical applications, the direct in-situ Rayleigh wave AEC measurement should be performed.

1. Introduction

Surface treatment, that is, a treatment of the surface and near-surface regions of a material to allow the surface to perform functions that are distinct from those functions demanded from the bulk of the material (ASM Handbook), is one of the essential aspects in the design of high-performance components in the aerospace industry [1]. Among the variety of different methods, the shot peening (SP), laser shock peening (LSP), and low plasticity burnishing (LPB) treatments allow for a significant increase in the high-cycle fatigue properties [2] and to improve foreign object damage resistance [3] for the gas turbine components.

The core of the aforementioned methods is the introduction of a compressive residual stress layer in the surface of a structural element (i.e., leading edge of fan blades or turbine disc), which retards the crack growth. SP, as the most convenient technique, is widely used during both the manufacturing and MRO (maintenance, repair, and operations) procedures, in order to improve the fatigue performance of elements and increase the life expectancy of an aircraft part.

Currently, industrial and in-field applications are used to validate the intensity of SP with a series of Almen stripes measurements—treated coupons with known properties. Semidestructive (borehole drilling) and destructive (slicing) methods are also used as reference. Only the laboratory NDE methods (electron, X-ray, or neutron diffraction) have proven its versatility for stress–strain state evaluation for a wide range of metals [4]. The general motivation for the current research is to contribute to the fundamental knowledge, necessary for the development of in-field nondestructive residual stress measurement.

The application of ultrasonic testing (UT) for evaluation of the material properties is one of the standard approaches [5].

This research is funded from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement N. 722134 - NDTonAIR

 serghey.gartsev@ikts.fraunhofer.de (S. Gartsev)
ORCID(s): 0000-0001-8813-7068 (S. Gartsev)

In particular, the stress–strain state can be determined with use of acoustoelastic effect—the dependency of the phase velocity of an elastic wave on the actual stress–strain state [6]. The dependency of the velocity on stress is described through the material's nonlinear elastic properties, expressed as the acoustoelastic constants (AEC), or the third-order elastic constants (TOEC) [7, 8, 9, 10]. For the problem of stress determination, these constants have to be known either from the literature or by calibration with a known (e.g., applied) stress level. Defined first for the bulk wave in an isotropic solid, the theoretical description of the acoustoelastic effect has been extended for Rayleigh waves (RW) [11, 12], and also proved experimentally [13, 14].

As the residual stress level in the surface-treated materials varies with depth [2], the use of Rayleigh waves appears beneficial due to the ability to control the penetration depth with the frequency. Published works indicate that estimation of the surface layer stress with the acoustoelastic effect is possible in principle; however, they also highlight the fundamental challenges [15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20]. The main difficulty, in this case, is that the surface wave velocity is not only influenced directly by stress via the acoustoelastic effect but also by the microstructural changes due to plastic deformation (cold work). Therefore, at least two contributions affecting the Rayleigh wave velocity variation must be separated.

Moreover, the AEC, which express the material nonlinearity, are known to vary with the plastic deformation [15], which is introduced in tandem with the residual stress by the surface treatment. Finally, only a few results for the relevant superalloys are available [16, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22]. In summary, residual stress measurement of surface treated materials with UT is a complex problem with several open questions. The aim of the present paper is to fill the gap related to the Rayleigh wave AEC of some relevant materials and their determination by direct and indirect measurements.

In this paper, we determine the Rayleigh wave AEC for the available In718 and Ti6246 samples in two different ways.

The first method is the direct measurement of the surface acoustic wave velocity under the different sample load states. The second, indirect way, is measuring the material bulk wave AEC (BW AEC) and mapping these constants through known formulas for the isotropic materials to calculate the sequence BW AEC \rightarrow TOEC \rightarrow RW AEC. The results obtained are compared with each other and with the few available literature values for the given materials. Direct measurements of RW AEC for the shot peened material were performed for the first time, to the best of the authors' knowledge.

2. Theoretical background

In the general case of elastic wave propagation in an isotropic body, strained with uniaxial load (let us define the load direction as '1' for convention), acoustoelastic constants can be defined as follows:

$$L_{ij} = \frac{\delta V_{ij}/V_{ij}^0}{\delta \epsilon} \quad (1)$$

where the first subindex shows the wave propagation direction in a Cartesian coordinate system, and the second subindex shows the particle displacement direction for a given wave. ϵ is a strain level in direction '1', and V^0 stands for the velocity at zero axial strain.

The analytical expressions for the variation of velocity of the bulk wave in a pre-stressed isotropic solid were published first by Hughes and Kelly [6], based on Murnaghan's theory of finite deformations of solids [7]. In terms of strain invariants I_1, I_2, I_3 , strain energy per unit mass can be written as:

$$\phi = \frac{1}{2}(\lambda + 2\mu)I_1^2 - 2\mu I_2 + \frac{1}{3}(l + 2m)I_1^3 - 2mI_1 I_2 + nI_3 \quad (2)$$

where λ and μ are the second-order elastic constants in Lamé notation, and l, m, n are the third-order elastic constants (TOEC) in Murnaghan notation, correspondingly. According to [6], there are three real solutions for the plane wave propagation equation, and the particle velocities for the three solutions are orthogonal. Therefore, dimensionless BW AEC for the case of uniaxial load, acting in a direction '1', may be written as [5, 6]:

$$L_{21} = \frac{\lambda + 2\mu + m}{2(\lambda + \mu)} + \frac{\nu n}{4\mu} \quad (3)$$

$$L_{22} = -2\nu(1 + \frac{m - \mu l / \lambda}{\lambda + 2\mu}) \quad (4)$$

$$L_{23} = \frac{m - 2\lambda}{2(\lambda + \mu)} - \frac{n}{4\mu} \quad (5)$$

where ν is the Poisson ratio.

Therefore, AEC (or TOEC) may be determined for the given λ and μ with three independent measurements. In our

Figure 1: Polarisation convention. P- pressure wave, S - shear wave with 2 possible polarizations. Load direction 1 is shown with the grey arrows. Equations 3-5: $L_{21} \leftrightarrow S_{\parallel}$, $L_{22} \leftrightarrow P$, $L_{23} \leftrightarrow S_{\perp}$. Equation 6: $\beta_{11} \leftrightarrow RW_{\parallel}$, $\beta_{33} \leftrightarrow RW_{\perp}$

Figure 2: Principal measurement scheme (DS—Digital scope; LDV—laser Doppler vibrometer; ADC—analogue-to-digital conversion). Bulk wave acoustoelastic constant (BW AEC) measurements are shown with a dashed line.

case, the L_{22} has been measured with a pressure wave transducer, L_{21} , with a shear wave with particle displacement parallel to the load direction, and L_{23} , with a shear wave with particle displacement normal to the load direction (Figure 1). The values of the Lamé constants have been obtained with velocity measurements with no load and a known density.

For the surface acoustic wave case, RW AEC can be defined either in a similar way to Equation 1, as the ratio of the relative RW velocity change to strain ϵ [12, 23], or, more common, as the ratio of the relative RW velocity change to stress σ [14, 24]. For the RW propagating in direction '1' on the free surface (the '1'-'3' plane) of an isotropic material, the RW AEC β_{ii} can be defined as [14]:

$$\frac{\Delta V}{V^0} = \beta_{11}\sigma_{11} + \beta_{33}\sigma_{33} \quad (6)$$

RW AEC can be evaluated from the TOEC values via Grüneisen constants, which describe the strain dependence of the lattice vibrational frequencies ([25], Equation 4.22).

Figure 3: Samples geometry and shot peening (SP) scheme. The treated areas are illustrated by gray and the treating intensity in Almen (A) is indicated. Sample 1 (upper) is treated from both sides with intensity 5 A and 8 A, and sample 2 (bottom) is peened from a single side. The sample thicknesses are 4.8 mm and 3.8 mm, respectively. Sample 2 has rounded edges to allow the RW exited at the back surface to propagate to the front (see the text). The load direction 1 is shown with gray arrows.

3. Samples and the experimental setup

The principal design of the experiment is shown in Figure 2. Four available metal samples with two different shapes, machined from Inconel 718 and Titanium 6246 alloys, have been used for the measurements. They had been already plastically deformed (with $\sim 1\%$ maximum strain). The samples were tested, annealed and measured again. Finally, each sample was shot-peened with 5 Almen and 8 Almen intensity at the selected surface areas and the direct RW AEC measurements were performed again. The sample geometry and the surface-treated-area layout are shown in Figure 3. The sample type 1 and 2 (upper/lower drawing in Figure 3) are used for the measurements with RW propagation parallel/perpendicular to the load direction, respectively. In the latter case the transducer was placed at the opposite side due to space limitation. The edges of that sample had been rounded to allow the RW propagate from backside to the front side without strong reflection. BW AEC values have been measured at 5 different measurement points of sample 1.

In all measurements a ZwickRoell tensile machine has been used for the initiation of external uniform tensile strains on specimens at eight different levels at the ambient conditions. The actual strain of the sample was measured by means of a tensile machine extensometer. The effects related to sample heating, have been neglected.

For the measurement of BW AEC, the pressure and shear wave ultrasonic transducers, clamped normally to the sample surface, have been used both for the elastic wave generation and for the multiple echo signal recording. An excitation pulse was generated with a pulser-receiver (Olympus 5900PR). The received signal was conditioned with the same

Figure 4: Rayleigh wave pulse shape and spectra for three commercial transducers with different f_c .

pulser-receiver and recorded with a high-end digital scope (LeCroy 62 Xi-A, 10 GS/s, 8 bit). For the evaluation of three AEC values for the isotropic material, BW measurements with the three possible polarisations have been performed (see the Figure 1 and the Equations 3–5). Each sample was measured at five different points.

For the direct RW AEC measurements, the ultrasonic transducer on a wedge was attached to the sample. The wedge angle was selected for the generation of the Rayleigh wave. Three commercial transducers with different nominal central frequencies f_c (1.5 MHz, 5 MHz, and 10 MHz) were used for the excitation. The waveform and the frequency spectra of the excited Rayleigh wave are presented for each transducer in Figure 4. For the recording of velocity variation, contactless laser Doppler vibrometer (LDV) scans were performed at several lines, parallel to the wave propagation direction. For the RW_{\parallel} propagation direction, Sample 1 was used and both the excitation and recording were done at the same face. For the RW_{\perp} case, Sample 2 was used, where the Rayleigh wave was generated at the backside and traveled around the half-round edge into the scan area (see also the [21] and Figure 3). The acquired signal was recorded with the analog-to-digital conversion (ADC) board (GaGe 14200, 200 MS/s, 8 bit).

Table 1

Third-order elastic constants (TOEC) values, calculated from measured BW AEC for annealed samples

Material	l , GPa	m , GPa	n , GPa
In718 (5 points)	-556 ± 5	-624 ± 5	-484 ± 5
In718 (3 points) [19]	-524 ± 4	-603 ± 4	-478 ± 2.3
In718 (3 points) [22]	-472 ± 19	-564 ± 15	-489 ± 7
Ti6246 (5 points)	-312 ± 125	-309 ± 71	-442 ± 51
Ti6246 (3 points) [19]	-356 ± 35	-390 ± 21	-475 ± 15

4. Data acquisition and processing

For both types of experiment, the broadband pulse signal was sent to the transducer with a given central frequency and bandwidth, and then, the delayed signal was recorded with several hundreds of averagings. The collected data were processed in the MATLAB and Python 3.7 environments. With several variations, dependent on data acquisition systems, the general processing strategy looked as follows:

1. Raw data filtering in the bandwidth of interest with FIR (finite impulse response) or DWT (discrete wavelet transform) filter.
2. Extracting the cross-correlation function peaks time delay.
3. Propagation velocity estimation based on the line fit in the (real travel path, cross-correlation peak delay) space.

The influence of probe/wedge geometry was neglected for both cases.

4.1. Bulk waves

The multiple echo signal was recorded with a high-resolution digital scope, allowing us to accurately extract the elastic wave velocity for the relatively short traveling distance. An example of the recorded multiple-echo signal and extracted cross-correlation peaks is shown in Figure 5. For each of the three possible polarizations, the dependency of the velocity variation on applied loads was measured at five different points. The results of the measurements are shown in Table 1 and Figure 6. Measurements of BW AEC have been performed with the samples in the annealed state.

4.2. Rayleigh waves

For the extraction of the surface acoustic wave velocity dependence on the applied load, a series of contactless scans were performed with a LDV (laser Doppler vibrometer), mounted on the 3-axis scanner. The acoustoelastic constants have been measured for the Rayleigh wave, traveling parallel and normal to the load direction. The recorded propagation distance for the treated and non-treated cases was in the range of 30–45 mm for the different sample types. The out-of-plane component of displacement was scanned along five to eight parallel lines with a 1 mm step and 1 mm line offset. The additional procedure for the velocity extraction

Figure 5: Multiple echo signal processing example. Upper figure - raw signal (filtered) and cross-correlation function with extracted peaks. Lower figure - fit result.

was needed, due to the rather low SNR (signal-to-noise ratio) level of the LDV measurements, especially for the treated samples at higher frequencies. Each scan line was treated independently as a B-scan, and processed as follows:

1. Selection of the point with the highest SNR (reference point).
2. Calculation of the cross-correlation function between the reference point and given point at the scan line.
3. Extraction of the cross-correlation function maximum time delay (between the reference point and given point).
4. Estimation of the RW velocity by the linear approximation in the (scanner coordinate–cross-correlation peak delay) space with an iterative algorithm, the random sample and consensus (RANSAC) [26].

RANSAC, or random sample and consensus algorithm, is an iterative algorithm to estimate the model parameters in the presence of *outliers*. In the present case, outliers were defined as points with an SNR lower than the threshold level, or the secondary peaks, extracted from the cross-correlation function. In general, RANSAC consists of two iterative stages:

1. Select the random minimal sample set (2 points for the line scan) from the input dataset (B-scan) to fit the model.
2. Add the points to the sample set, which are consistent with the model with a predefined error.

Figure 6: Relative velocity variation of the bulk wave modes due to uniaxial strain load (mean values and standard deviation for 5 different measurement points) for In718 and Ti6246 alloys. P - pressure wave, S - shear wave with two possible polarizations (see Figure 1).

The procedure is stopped if the fit quality target value or the maximum number of iterations is reached. The threshold and fit quality parameters have been selected manually. An example of the B-scan processing with the RANSAC algorithm is shown in Figure 7.

An example of velocity variation extraction for the β evaluation for the In718 is shown in Figure 8.

5. Results

TOEC values, mapped from the direct BW AEC measurements, and the comparison with the published results are given in Table 1. The available results for the In718 sample are in reasonable correlation with the measured values. The high scattering of Ti6246 nonlinear elastic constant values was expected from previous works [19], and can be explained by the variation in the microstructural properties, which is beyond the scope of the current work.

The results of RW AEC extraction for the samples with different treatment are shown in Table 2. A different history means the same samples have been measured after plastic deformation, annealing, and shot-peening. RW AEC have been measured with the transducers with different central frequency and bandwidth, which gives the different penetration depth (approximately 7 treatment depths (TD) for 1.5

Figure 7: B scan processing example. Upper figure—raw B-scan; middle figure—raw record at the given point and result of filtering; bottom figure—result of iterative fitting.

MHz, 2 TD for 5 MHz and 1 TD for 10 MHz transducer, correspondingly). This table includes the values, mapped from the annealed sample BW AEC measurements (marked with bold), and the few published results. Mapping was done with the Lamé constants, obtained with the literature values for density and the BW velocity measurements at the zero load ($\rho_{In} = 8220 \text{ kg/m}^3$, $V_{In}^P = 5814 \text{ m/s}$, $V_{In}^S = 3096 \text{ m/s}$, $\rho_{Ti} = 4650 \text{ kg/m}^3$, $V_{Ti}^P = 6126 \text{ m/s}$, $V_{Ti}^S = 3150 \text{ m/s}$).

Figure 8: Results of the measurements of β_{33} for In718 at $f_c=5\text{MHz}$. 0A, 5A and 8A stand for shot peening intensity in Almen units (no peening/mild/strong)

Table 2

Direct-measured RW AEC for the different states of material and comparison with the literature and mapped values (here, PD—plastically deformed; AA—after annealing; **BW** - mapped from the BW AEC measurements, available literature values are shown with the reference number). Treatment and measurements at 0A, 5A, 8A states have been performed after annealing.

Material	$f_c(\text{MHz})$	$\beta_{11}(1/\text{TPa})$	$\beta_{33}(1/\text{TPa})$
In718 (PD)	1.5	-4.11 ± 3.89	-1.73 ± 3.03
In718 (AA)	1.5	3.39 ± 0.66	-0.92 ± 0.77
<i>In718 ([21])</i>		2.36	-1.20
In718 (BW)		2.18 ± 0.07	-1.31 ± 0.03
In718 (0A)	1.5	-0.49 ± 0.78	
In718 (0A)	5	0.38 ± 2.90	-7.98 ± 1.47
In718 (0A)	10	0.23 ± 2.81	
In718 (5A)	5	-1.27 ± 2.80	-6.88 ± 2.48
In718 (5A)	10	-0.95 ± 1.84	
In718 (8A)	5	-2.40 ± 4.33	-2.51 ± 1.80
In718 (8A)	10	6.06 ± 1.25	
Ti6246 (PD)	1.5	0.32 ± 2.60	-2.36 ± 3.20
Ti6246 (AA)	1.5	3.36 ± 0.25	1.46 ± 2.10
<i>Ti6246 ([21])</i>		2.79	1.62
Ti6246 (BW)		3.3 ± 2	5.81 ± 1.97
Ti6246 (0A)	5	7.83 ± 4.19	1.61 ± 1.22
Ti6246 (5A)	5	6.25 ± 4.42	3.65 ± 1.72
Ti6246 (8A)	5	3.42 ± 3.59	7.66 ± 2.99

As can be seen, the measured values of the β_{ii} constants are dependent on the material state. BW AEC \rightarrow TOEC \rightarrow RW AEC mapping (indirect measurement method) yields the results close to directly measured values only for the β_{11}^{Ti} . The reasons of deviation of the rest mapped RW AEC from the directly measured values needs further investigation.

In Figure 9, the parameter β_{11} , measured for the three different states of the single In718 sample, is depicted with

Figure 9: In718 β_{11} for three different sample states (all without treatment, 0 A—measurements at nontreated part of the treated sample), $f_c=1.5$ MHz.

Figure 10: RW AEC variation for 0 Almen (nontreated), 5 Almen, and 8 Almen shot-peening intensity for In718 and Ti6246 alloys, $f_c = 5$ MHz. Vertical axis— β_{11} ; horizontal axis— β_{33}

a vertical bar chart. These states are shown on the horizontal axis: the sample after annealing, after the partial surface treatment (measurements done at nontreated area), and after the plastic deformation. Due to the apparent anomaly behavior, measurements for the 0A state have been repeated for several times, but always have shown the similar result. Both the magnitude and the sign of RW AEC are dependent on the In718 alloy treatment history.

The effect of the shot-peening intensity on the sign and value of RW AEC for In718 and Ti6246 is depicted in Figure 10. In contrast with the titanium alloy, for which the 'cumulative' nonlinearity $\beta_{11} + \beta_{33}$ maintains the sign and magnitude, for the Inconel, both β constants undergo severe variations in magnitude and/or sign, therefore jeopardizing its following application for the surface-treated structure residual stress evaluation.

6. Discussion

In this paper, the problem of estimating the acoustoelastic constant of surface acoustic waves for mechanically processed superalloys has been considered. For the characterization of the surface treatment intensity with the use of ultrasonic waves, one should always account for the state of the material, penetration depth or bandwidth of interest, and wave propagation orientation.

The necessity of use of direct measurements has been shown through comparison with the BW AEC values, measured for the same samples and mapped to the RW AEC. In the given case, the existing theoretical model failed to predict the values obtained through direct measurement for the annealed samples, except for the β_{11}^{Ti} case. For the rest cases, the direct and mapped RW AEC values have shown a significant difference.

As shot-peened superalloys, RW AEC are highly sensitive to the treatment intensity and RW penetration depth. Thus, the aforementioned parameters should be determined in the actual region of interest, taking into account both the macro- and micro-structure of the material under test. The influence of the surface treatment on nonlinear elastic properties varies with the alloy type as well. Inconel alloy RW AEC tend to have stronger variations with the shot peening intensity, than the titanium alloy does.

Therefore, for practical applications—for example, for the retrieval of information regarding the treatment status and the stress–strain condition—the development of an in-field RW AEC/TOEC measurement method is essential. This task cannot be solved in one step, rather by filling the knowledge gaps, as in given contribution, and addressing the new questions in the following work.

Acknowledgements

The authors gratefully acknowledge Dr. Marek Rjelka from Fraunhofer IKTS for the AEC mapping calculation and fruitful collaboration, and Dr. Roland Hessert, Dr. Joachim Bamberg and Christina Preikszas from MTU Aero Engines AG for the meaningful conversations and the samples preparation.

One of the authors, Sergey Gartsev, gratefully acknowledges funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement N. 722134 - NDTonAIR.

References

- [1] W. Zhuang, B. Wicks, Mechanical surface treatment technologies for gas turbine engine components, *Journal of Engineering for Gas Turbines and Power* 125 (2003) 1021–1025.
- [2] L. Wagner, Mechanical surface treatments on titanium, aluminum and magnesium alloys, *Materials Science and Engineering: A* 263 (1999) 210–216.
- [3] T. E. Pistoichini, M. R. Hill, Effect of laser peening on fatigue performance in 300m steel, *Fatigue & Fracture of Engineering Materials & Structures* 34 (2011) 521–533.
- [4] P. Withers, H. Bhadeshia, Residual stress. part 1 – measurement techniques, *Materials Science and Technology* 17 (2001) 355–365.
- [5] D. E. Bray, R. K. Stanley, *Nondestructive evaluation: a tool in design, manufacturing and service*, CRC press, 1996.
- [6] D. S. Hughes, J. L. Kelly, Second-order elastic deformation of solids, *Physical Review* 92 (1953) 1145–1149.
- [7] F. Murnaghan, *Finite Deformation of an Elastic Solid*, New York (1951), John Wiley and Sons, 1951.
- [8] L. Landau, E. Lifshitz, *Theory of elasticity*, 3rd, Pergamon Press 3 (1986).
- [9] D. Husson, G. S. Kino, A perturbation theory for acoustoelastic effects, *Journal of Applied Physics* 53 (1982) 7250–7258.
- [10] S. Takahashi, R. Motegi, Stress dependency on ultrasonic wave propagation velocity, *Journal of Materials Science* 22 (1987) 1857–1863.
- [11] Y. Iwashimizu, The rayleigh wave in a finitely deformed isotropic elastic material, *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America* 64 (1978) 910.
- [12] M. Hirao, H. Fukuoka, K. Hori, Acoustoelastic effect of rayleigh surface wave in isotropic material, *Journal of Applied Mechanics* 48 (1981) 119–124.
- [13] A. Zeiger, K. Jassby, Measurement of acoustoelastic coefficients of rayleigh waves in steel alloys, *Journal of Nondestructive Evaluation* 3 (1982) 115–124.
- [14] D. Husson, A perturbation theory for the acoustoelastic effect of surface waves, *Journal of Applied Physics* 57 (1985) 1562–1568.
- [15] P. B. Nagy, Opportunities and challenges for nondestructive residual stress assessment, in: *AIP Conference Proceedings*, AIP, 2006. doi:10.1063/1.2184508.
- [16] B. Köhler, M. Barth, F. Schubert, J. Bamberg, H.-U. Baron, D. O. Thompson, D. E. Chimenti, Characterization of surface treated aero-engine alloys by rayleigh wave velocity dispersion, in: *Conference*, AIP, 2010. doi:10.1063/1.3362402.
- [17] M. Liu, J.-Y. Kim, L. Jacobs, J. Qu, Experimental study of nonlinear rayleigh wave propagation in shot-peened aluminum plates—feasibility of measuring residual stress, *NDT & E International* 44 (2011) 67–74.
- [18] M. Barth, M. Küttner, B. Köhler, J. Bamberg, H.-U. Baron, Universal ultrasonic goniometer for rayleigh and surface skimming longitudinal wave dispersion measurements, in: *Conference*, AIP, 2012. doi:10.1063/1.4716439.
- [19] M. Rjelka, M. Barth, S. Reinert, B. Koehler, J. Bamberg, H. U. Baron, R. Hessert, Third order elastic constants and rayleigh wave dispersion of shot peened aero-engine materials, *Materials Science Forum* 768-769 (2013) 201–208.
- [20] S. Hubel, A. Dillhöfer, H. Rieder, M. Spies, J. Bamberg, J. Götz, R. Hessert, C. Preikszas, Ultrasonic evaluation of residual stresses in aero engine materials using bulk and rayleigh surface waves, *AIP Publishing LLC*, 2014. doi:10.1063/1.4864876.
- [21] B. Köhler, M. Barth, J. Bamberg, H.-U. Baron, Rayleigh wave velocity dispersion for characterization of surface treated aero engine alloys, in: *Proceedings of the ECNDT*, 2010.
- [22] S. Hubel, M. Spies, H. Rieder, A. Dillhoefer, J. Bamberg, R. Hessert, C. Preikszas, Basic investigations to establish an ultrasonic stress evaluation technique for aero engine materials, *NDT in Aerospace* 2012 - Th.1.B.3 (2012).
- [23] Y.-C. Lee, J. O. Kim, J. D. Achenbach, Measurement of stresses by line-focus acoustic microscopy, *Ultrasonics* 32 (1994) 359–365.
- [24] M. Duquenooy, M. Ouafthouh, M. Ourak, F. Jenot, Theoretical determination of rayleigh wave acoustoelastic coefficients: comparison with experimental values, *Ultrasonics* 39 (2002) 575–583.
- [25] A. P. Mayer, Surface acoustic waves in nonlinear elastic media, *Physics Reports* 256 (1995) 237–366.
- [26] S. Choi, T. Kim, W. Yu, Performance evaluation of RANSAC family (2009).